

MANUFACTURE OF FIBER GLASS REINFORCED PLASTIC
POLES BY PRESS MOLDING METHOD

by

Williams P. Kao, Ph.D.*

1. Current market position of frp light poles in Taiwan.
2. Frp light poles properties.
3. Review of various pole manufacturing methods:
 - a. Filament winding method.
 - b. Centrifugal casting method.
 - c. Matched die press molding.
4. Press molding method:
 - a. Unidirectional smc.
 - b. Straight pole manufacturing.
 - c. Curved extender manufacturing.
 - d. Joint method.
5. Analysis and comparison among these manufacturing methods.
6. Conclusion.

* Tung Hsing FRP Corporation
P.O.Box 24-868
Taipei, Taiwan